

STRAIN AND STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN A ROTATING DISK MADE BY 2D C/C LAMINATED COMPOSITES

Fenghua Zhou, Akinori Ogawa and Ryosaku Hashimoto

*Aeroengine Division, National Aerospace Laboratory
7-44-1 Jindaijihigashi, Chofu, Tokyo 182-8522, JAPAN*

SUMMARY: Spin tests of 2D laminated C/C disks have been performed to study the materials' deformation and bursting failure properties under centrifugal loading. The strain distributions on disk-shape specimens were measured in the tests. In this paper, we use the *composite mechanics* method to analyze the stress and strain states within the C/C specimen. Firstly, classical laminate theory is used to deduce the in-plane elastic constants of the composites. Then, to analyze the complicated deformation behavior of an orthotropic rotating disk, a Ritz-type elastic analysis based on variation theory was proposed. By adequately assuming the deformation functions, the distributions of displacement, strain and stress components within the disk are accurately calculated. The calculated results are compared with the experimental measurement, from which the elastic constants of the unidirectional C/C lamina are determined. The failure phenomena of different specimen are discussed. From measured bursting velocity, the shearing strength of the UD-lamina is estimated.

KEYWORDS: C/C Composites, 2D Laminates; Rotating Disk, Ritz Method Elastic Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced carbon matrix composites (C/C composites) have excellent properties of retaining strength at high temperature up to 2000°C, good stiffness, light weightness, low thermal expansion coefficient, *etc.* These properties make the composite a good candidate material in high-temperature aerospace structures. A potential use of C/C composite is manufacturing high temperature rotating components^[1]. There are numerous reports on the developments and applications of these materials (for example, [2, 3]). However, because of the following reasons: 1. The mechanical properties of C/C composites are strongly dependent on their manufacturing process; 2. These materials are expensive so that generally there are not many specimens for testing; 3. The experimental methods for testing these materials/components are not mature; *etc.*, the fundamental data of C/C composites, especially those important for designing a rotating component, is not sufficient.

In the authors' research group, systematic investigation on C/C composites is performed, aiming to develop a turbine blisk (bladed disk) rotor with 3D woven C/C composite. In the fundamental phase of this project, tensile, bending, and spin test experiments of different 2D

laminated C/C composites were performed to investigate the materials mechanical properties. A summary of these researches can be found in Ref. [4]. From the tensile tests, it is found that [0/90] laminated C/C composites have orthotropic elastic properties, with very high elastic modules in fiber directions (E_{xx} and E_{yy}), but very low in-plane shearing modulus (G_{xy}) and very small Poisson's ratio (ν_{xy}). Spin tests of C/C composites, laminated in [0/90] and [0/45/-45/90] sequences, were performed to study the deformation and failure (bursting) properties of these materials under centrifugal loading. It was found that the failures of the specimen were due to the in-plane shear stress of each layer. The bursting speed of [0/90] composites was about 50-60% that of [0/45/-45/90] composites.

As one kind of fiber reinforced composites, the C/C laminate plate can be analyzed by the structural analytical method frequently used to fiber-reinforced-plastics (FRP). As a trial, we measured the elastic constants of unidirectional (UD) C/C composites by off-axis tensile experiments, and used the resulting data to predict the mechanical properties of multilayer C/C laminates. We found that classical laminate plate theory can be applied to predict 2D laminated C/C composites quite well^[5].

In the present paper, we will analyze the deformation and failure properties of 2D laminated C/C composite disk under centrifugal loading. Firstly, we give a brief account of experimental results. Then, we apply the classical laminate theory to deduce the expressions of the in-plane elastic constants for [0/90] and [0/45/-45/90] laminate plates. We propose a Ritz-type elastic analyzing approach based on variation theory, to calculate the stress of a rotating orthotropic disk. By adequately assuming the deformation functions of the rotating disk, the mechanical state variables: *displacement*, *strain* and *stress* on the disk can be evaluated quickly and accurately. By comparing the results of analysis and experiments, the basic mechanical parameters of the materials: *elastic constants*, *shearing strength*, *etc.*, are determined. The bursting phenomenon of different specimens will be explained finally.

TEST MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

The 2D laminated C/C composites being tested were manufactured by following sequences: 1. The unidirectional carbon fiber cloth plies are stacked to form the plate; 2. The plate is pitch impregnated and carbonized; 3. The impregnation and carbonization processes are repeated in multiple cycles to form the densified materials. Two kinds of laminates were manufactured: the **CC-2** laminate with [0/90]_{ns} (cross-ply) stacking sequence; and the **CC-3** laminate with the [0/45/-45/90]_{ns} (quasi-isotropic) stacking sequence. Thin, circular disk-type specimens were cut from the laminates. The dimensions of the specimen were: internal diameter $2a=100mm$, external diameter $2b=160mm$. The experiments were performed in a spin-test apparatus, where the specimen was rotated by an air-driven turbine. Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b are the photographs of the test facility and the specimen before testing.

Two types of the spin-test experiments: *non-failure test* and *failure test* were performed. In the non-failure test, the rotating speed of the specimen was low. During the test, the strain components on different points of the specimen (**A**: $r=65mm$, $\theta=0^\circ$ and **B**: $r=65mm$, $\theta=45^\circ$) were measured by a slip-ring measuring system. Fig. 2 illustrates the measuring points on the specimen surface and the controlling/measuring system.

Fig.1 (a) Spin test facility; (b) C/C specimen before testing

Strain measurement systems

Fig.2 (a) Strain measuring points on the specimen; (b) Strain measuring system

After non-failure test, the rotating speed was increased until the specimen was broken by centrifugal force (*failure test*). The rotating speed at which specimen broke was recorded as *bursting speed*. The appearance of specimen at the instant of bursting was photographed by a special photographic system where the stroboscopic lamp was triggered by the burst-sensing circuit. Details of the experiments were reported in Refs. [6] and [7]. In Fig. 3 the snapshots of specimen at bursting were shown. The broken specimens were shown in Fig. 4. The bursting speeds of different materials were listed in Table 1.

Fig.3 Bursting instants of C/C specimen: (a) [0/90] specimen; (b) [0/45/-45/90] specimen

Fig.4 Specimen after burst: (a) [0/90] specimen; (b) [0/45/-45/90] specimen

TABLE 1 BURSTING SPEED OF DIFFERENT C/C LAMINATES

	Lamination	Bursting Speed
CC-2	[0/90] _{ns}	27600 rpm
CC-3	[0/45/-45/90] _{ns}	49500 rpm

IN-PLANE ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF 2D C/C LAMINATES

For a unidirectional lamina of C/C material, there are four in-plane elastic constants: the elastic modulus in fiber direction E_L , elastic modulus in transverse direction E_T , the shearing modulus G_{LT} , and the Poisson's ratio ν_{LT} . When the UD lamina were stacked to form a 2D laminate plate (Fig. 5), the elastic parameters of the laminate plate can be calculated from the UD lamina elastic constants, by using classical laminate theory. Detailed deducting procedures are omitted here, which can be found in a *composite mechanics* textbook (e.g., [8]). In case of the [0/90] cross-ply laminate, the engineering elastic parameters in x- and y-directions are identical. Orthotropic property like this is called *cubic anisotropy*, there are three independent in-plane elastic constants, which are expressed as:

$$E_x = E_y = \frac{E_L^2 + 2E_L E_T + E_T^2 (1 - 4\nu_{LT}^2)}{2(E_L + E_T)(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T/E_L)} \quad (1)$$

$$\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx} = \frac{2\nu_{LT} E_T}{E_L + E_T}, \quad G_{xy} = G_{LT}$$

The [0/90] cross-ply laminate has the property of orthotropic elasticity. We define the orthotropic parameter α , by the following formula:

$$\alpha = \frac{2(1 - \nu_{xy})G_{xy}}{E_{xx}} = \frac{4(E_L + E_T - 2\nu_{LT} E_T)(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T/E_L)G_{LT}}{E_L^2 + 2E_L E_T + E_T^2 (1 - 4\nu_{LT}^2)} \quad (2)$$

Ordinarily, $E_T \ll E_L$, $G_{LT} \ll E_L$, it can be estimated that for a cross-ply laminate, $\nu_{xy} \ll 1$, $\alpha \ll 1$, the material has strong orthotropic property.

Fig.5 [0/90] Laminate: fiber oriented in x-, y-directions

On the other hand, For the [0/45/-45/90] laminate, the elastic constants are as following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_x = E_y &= \frac{[E_L + E_T(1 + 2\nu_{LT})][E_L + E_T(1 - 2\nu_{LT}) + 4G_{LT}(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T / E_L)]}{(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T / E_L)[3E_L + E_T(3 + 2\nu_{LT}) + 4G_{LT}(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T / E_L)]} \\
 \nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx} &= \frac{E_L + E_T(1 + 6\nu_{LT}) - 4G_{LT}(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T / E_L)}{3E_L + E_T(3 + 2\nu_{LT}) + 4G_{LT}(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T / E_L)} \\
 G_{xy} &= \frac{E_L + E_T(1 - 2\nu_{LT}) + 4G_{LT}(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T / E_L)}{8(1 - \nu_{LT}^2 E_T / E_L)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

It is seen that for this laminate, the relationship $G = E/2(1 - \nu)$ is satisfied. In other words, the orthotropic parameter $\alpha=1$. The material's elastic constants are identical in all directions, *i.e.*, material is *quasi-isotropic*.

ORTHOTROPIC DISK UNDER CENTRIFUGAL LOADING: ELASTIC ANALYSIS

The problem to be analyzed is shown in Fig. 6. For an (quasi-) isotropic rotating disk whose elastic constants are expressed by (3), the closed-form elastic solution exists that can be found in most textbooks of *elasticity*. However, for a rotating disk with cubic anisotropy as described by (1), no exact solution exists. Ordinarily, FEM calculation is used to analyze this problem. Although FEM analysis can be easily performed, it outputs huge amount of discrete data, which is difficult to sort out for further analysis. Moreover, the calculation accuracy for the stress is not high in FEM analysis unless fine meshes are used.

Fig.6 Analyzing problem: a rotating disk as the spin test specimen

We have developed a *Ritz-type* elastic analyzing approach based on variation theory to analyze this problem. The elastic analysis procedures are as following:

In polar coordinate system, the disk's displacement components in radial direction u_r , and in circumferential direction u_θ , are functions of the geometric coordinate (r, θ) :

$$u_r = u_r(r, \theta) \quad , \quad u_\theta = u_\theta(r, \theta) \quad (4)$$

The strain components are then expressed as:

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \quad , \quad \varepsilon_\theta = \frac{u_r}{r} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{r \partial \theta} \quad , \quad \gamma_{r\theta} = \frac{\partial u_r}{r \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{u_\theta}{r} \quad (5)$$

The total potential energy of the rotating disk system are calculated by integration:

$$W = \int_{r=a}^b \int_{\theta=0}^{2\pi} r \Psi(r, \theta) dr d\theta = \int_{r=a}^b \int_{\theta=0}^{2\pi} r (\Psi_e + \Psi_w) dr d\theta \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where: } \Psi_e = \frac{1}{2} \{ \varepsilon_r, \varepsilon_\theta, \gamma_{r\theta} \} [\tilde{E}(\theta)] \{ \varepsilon_r, \varepsilon_\theta, \gamma_{r\theta} \}^T \quad , \quad \Psi_w = -\rho \omega^2 u_r \quad (7)$$

are the densities of potential energy originated from deformation and centrifugal loading, respectively.

If the displacement functions u_r and u_θ are expressed by certain algebraic equations containing unknown coefficients, the total system potential W can be calculated by integration throughout the whole circular area. With the condition that W should take the minimum value, unknown coefficients in the deformation functions are calculated.

We found, with experience, that if displacement functions (4) take the form:

$$\begin{aligned} u_r &= (a_1 r^{-3} + a_2 r^{-1} + a_3 r + a_4 r^3 + a_5 r^5) + (b_1 r^{-3} + b_2 r^{-1} + b_3 r + b_4 r^3 + b_5 r^5) \cos(4\theta) \\ u_\theta &= (c_1 r^{-3} + c_2 r^{-1} + c_3 r + c_4 r^3 + c_5 r^5) \sin(4\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where a_i , b_i and c_i (totally 15) are unknown coefficients, then the present problem can be solved with satisfactory accuracy^[9].

COMPARISON OF CALCULATION RESULTS AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The elastic constants of UD-C/C lamina are listed in Table 2. These data are substituted into (1) and (3), to calculate the elastic constantans of two C/C laminates: CC-2 and CC-3 (Table 3). In Table 3 is also listed the orthotropic parameter α .

TABLE 2 ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF UD C/C PLY

E_L (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	G_{LT} (GPa)	ν_{LT}	ρ (Kg/m ³)
251.1	2.454	7.0	0.41	1630

TABLE 3 ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF C/C LAMINATES

	E_x (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	α
CC-2	127	7.0	0.00794	0.1111
CC-3	90.51	35	0.2930	1

Using the data shown in Table 3, the displacement, strain and stress of the rotating disk

are calculated. Fig. 7 shows the distribution of circumferential strain ε_r , radial strain ε_θ and the shear strain $\varepsilon_{r\theta}$. The rotating velocity of the disk is $18020rpm$. The units of the strain components are microns (μ).

Fig.7 Distribution of cylindrical strain components on [0/90] disk: (a) ε_r ; (b) ε_θ ; (c) $\varepsilon_{r\theta}$

Fig. 8 shows the changing of the strain values on **A** ($130mm, 0^\circ$) and **B** ($130mm, 45^\circ$) points with the increase of rotating velocity. The experimental data are also plotted in the figures for comparison. The calculation curves agree with the experimental results quite well.

Fig.8 ϵ_r and ϵ_θ on (130, 0) and (130, $\pi/4$) points: (a) [0/90] disk; (b) [0/45/-45/90] disk

FAILURE CHARACTERISTICS

From Fig. 3a, it can be found that the failure of [0/90] disk originated from four radial cracks propagating in 45° , 135° , 225° and 315° . As the result, the disk specimen broke into four parts (Fig. 4a). However, the failure patterns of [0/45/-45/90] specimen is complicated, the specimen burst to many small pieces under centrifugal loading (Fig. 4b).

The stress distributions on *every* ply of the two laminates is investigated. It is found that for [0/90] laminate, the maximum shearing stress (in reinforcing Fiber direction LT) appears at the same location of both 0° -ply and 90° -ply: the inner circle of 45° , 135° , 225° and 315° points (Fig. 9a). However, for [0/45/-45/90] laminate, the maximum shearing stress of 0° -ply and 90° -ply appears at 45° , 135° , 225° and 315° points, but those of 45° -ply and -45° -ply appears at 0° , 90° , 180° and 270° points (Fig. 9b). This explains the different failure phenomena observed in CC-2 and CC-3 disks.

The absolute values of the shearing stress for different materials are checked below. Fig. 10 compares the distribution of shearing stress in (LT) fiber-direction, τ_{LT} , on the 0° -ply of CC-2 disk and CC-3 disk, both under centrifugal loading of $18020rpm$. The maximum of τ_{LT} appears at the same location of the disk surfaces. The absolute values of $\tau_{LT}(max)$ on [0/90]

disk and on [0/45/-45/90] disk are 15.55Mpa and 3.38Mpa , respectively. The maximum τ_{LT} on [0/90] disk is more than 4 times as large as that on [0/45/-45/90] disk. This is the main reason that the burst speed of CC-2 disk is much less than the burst speed of CC-3 disk.

Fig.9 The points where maximum τ_{LT} appears: (a) [0/90] disk; (b) [0/45/-45/90] disk

Fig.10 Distribution of τ_{LT} on the 0-ply of: (a) [0/90] disk; (b) [0/45/-45/90] disk

The shear strength of UD-C/C ply is assumed to be 36Mpa . Based on the maximum shear stress failure theory, we can predict that the bursting velocity of CC-2 specimen and CC-3 specimen are $27,4000\text{rpm}$ and $58,800\text{rpm}$, respectively. This prediction agrees with the experimental result of CC-2 material. However, the predicted burst speed is larger than the experimental result of CC-3 materials. We believe that other stress components, the normal stress in fiber direction σ_L and in transversal direction σ_T , also play roles in composite failure. A more accurate prediction of composite failure may be made by using *stress energy failure criterion*.

CONCLUSION

Spin tests of two 2D laminated C/C composite disks, stacked in $[0/90]_{\text{ns}}$ and $[0/45/-45/90]_{\text{ns}}$ sequences, were performed. The characteristics of *strain distribution* and *specimen failure* differ very much for two materials. A mechanical analysis was performed to investigate the deformation and the stress properties of the two disks under centrifugal loading. The analytical results agree well with the experimental data. The failure phenomena of two materials are explained.

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